

EFFECT OF LOAD FREQUENCY ON THE TENSILE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF ANGLE-PLY AS4/PEEK

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of a study aimed at understanding the load frequency effect on fatigue life of thermoplastic composites. The tensile fatigue behaviour ($R=0.13$) of straight sided angle-ply $[\pm 45]_4$ s AS4/PEEK was investigated at three frequencies. The cyclic stress-strain data and temperature variation during fatigue tests were recorded. A model correlating the thermal effect to the load frequency on the fatigue life of the thermoplastic composite was proposed.

KEYWORDS: fatigue, load frequency, thermoplastic, hysteresis loop, thermal effect

INTRODUCTION

The load frequency is known to have a substantial effect on fatigue performance of polymer composites, especially on laminates dominated by the matrix properties [1-8]. Literature data indicate that the load frequency has a two-fold effect on fatigue of polymer composites: the creep effect and the thermal effect. Due to the viscoelastic nature of polymeric matrices, matrix dominated laminates tend to creep during low frequency fatigue testing and, hence, decreasing load frequency tends to reduce the fatigue strength of the material. On the other hand, the viscoelastic dissipation under cyclic loading leads to autoheating of the matrix material. The friction at damaged sites also generates heat. Since the heat generation is proportional to load frequency, increasing frequency would increase the temperature rise and, thus, result in softening of the material. Depending on the material system, the level and wave form of cyclic stress, increasing load frequency may either increase or decrease the fatigue life determined by the balance between the creep and thermal effects.

Fatigue failures associated with large-scale hysteretic heating have been observed in polymers [9,10] and in glass fiber reinforced epoxy [1] where fatigue life decreased as load frequency increased. The effect of hysteretic heating was less substantial in graphite/epoxy and consequently fatigue life increased as load frequency increased [3]. The same trend was observed in Boron/epoxy [6].

Several studies on fatigue of thermoplastic composite AS4/PEEK have shown that hysteretic heating in AS4/PEEK is much more pronounced as compared to that in thermoset composites [4,5,11] and the fatigue life decreases remarkably with increasing load frequency [4,5]. Dan-Jumbo et al [5] have developed a model to account for the load frequency effect on fatigue life. Their study, however, was conducted with notched specimens where the thermal effect is restricted as compared to that in smooth specimens because the heat generated at notch areas can dissipate into a much larger surrounding materials at lower stresses.

The present work is aimed at understanding the thermal effect associated with load frequency on fatigue life of thermoplastic composite AS4/PEEK. To emphasize the thermal effect, straight sided angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ specimens were used. Tensile-tensile fatigue tests were conducted at three frequencies. The cyclic stress-strain data and temperature variation during fatigue tests were recorded. A model correlating the thermal effect to the load frequency on the fatigue life of the thermoplastic composite was proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimens

AS4/PEEK $[0/90]_{4s}$ panels of 12x12 inches were made from prepreg using a WABASH hot press following ICI's procedure. The straight sided $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ specimens were then cut from the laminates. The nominal dimensions of the specimens were 200x18x2 mm with 38 mm long aluminum end tabs, which follows the specification of ASTM D3479. The ultimate tensile strength of the $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ laminates was measured to be 338 MPa, which was very close to the value reported in literature. Fig.1 shows the typical stress-strain curve obtained by static tensile tests.

Fatigue Test

The tensile-tensile fatigue tests were carried out using a MTS machine under load controlled mode with sinusoidal load wave form. The stress ratio in fatigue was $R=0.13$. Three load frequencies were investigated: 1 Hz, 5 Hz and 10 Hz. At each frequency, fatigue tests were conducted at three stress levels: 60%, 70% and 80% of the ultimate tensile strength. To complete the S-N curve, few more fatigue tests were conducted at other stress levels.

During fatigue tests, the load level was monitored from the signal of the load cell while the axial strain was measured using an extensormeter. The cyclic stress-strain data were collected at selected cycles. The temperatures were measured during the test using thermocouples attached to the center region of the specimen surface and recorded by a computer data acquisition system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

S-N Data

The data on fatigue strength - number of cycle to failure (S-N) obtained are presented in Table 1. The values of the equilibrium or the maximum temperature recorded during fatigue tests are also listed in Table 1. The S-N curves for three frequencies are plotted in Fig.2, where symbols are the test data. It is evident that increasing frequency reduced the fatigue life and this life reduction effect appeared to be larger at lower stress levels.

Fig.1 STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF ANGLE-PLY APC2/AS-4 UNDER STATIC LOADING

Fig.2 S-N curves of AS4/PEEK [±45]4s laminates.
 The symbols are test data and the dashed lines are the predictions by Eq.8.

Fig.3 Hysteresis loops during fatigue at 60% of the ultimate strength and

(a)1Hz, (b)5Hz, (c)10Hz at selected numbers of cycles

Fig.4 Hysteresis loop area vs. normalized fatigue life at (a)1Hz, (b)5Hz, and (c)10Hz

Fig.5 Temperature variation during fatigue at (a)60%, (b)70%, and (c)80% of the ultimate strength

Hysteresis Loop

Fig.3 shows the typical hysteresis loops recorded during fatigue tests at 60% stress level for the three load frequencies. As seen the shape of the hysteresis loops changed gradually during fatigue and the way of its change depended upon load frequency. Initially the hysteresis loop had a shape of slim ellipse and was symmetric to its center, which may be approximated by two triangles placed base to base as observed by other researchers [1]. With increasing the number of cycle, the loop nearly collapsed in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b (1 Hz and 5 Hz, respectively) but expanded in Fig 3c (10 Hz).

At other stress levels, the evolution of hysteresis loop also appeared to depend upon frequency. To compare the effect of frequency and stress level on the evolution of hysteresis loop, the area of hysteresis loop is plotted versus the normalized number of cycle N/N_f in Fig.4, where N_f is the fatigue life. At 1 Hz (Fig.4a), the area of hysteresis loop decreased as the number of cycles increased whereas at 5 Hz and 10 Hz (Fig.4b and Fig.4c) the trend reversed and this trend became stronger at higher stress levels.

The evolution of hysteresis loop correlated well with the damage extent observed on specimen surfaces. The main type of damage observed on fatigue failed specimens was matrix cracking. It was found that, with increasing load frequency and stress level, the intensity of the matrix cracks increased. The additional energy dissipation as reflected by the expanded hysteresis loops is likely due to friction at these damaged sites.

Another noticeable point in Fig.4 is the accumulation of creep strain. Regardless of the load frequency and stress level used, all specimens failed by fatigue exhibited a total maximum strain in the range of 18-20%, which is in the range of failure strain obtained by static tests.

Temperature Rise

The typical temperature variations during fatigue tests are shown in Fig.5 for the three load frequencies at three stress levels. At 1 Hz, temperature rise reached the equilibrium for fatigue tests conducted at all stress levels and the equilibrium temperature increased with stress levels. At 5 Hz, a peak in temperature rise curve, which is similar to that reported by [4], was observed at tests conducted at 60% level. At higher stress levels, monotonic temperature rises were recorded. At 10 Hz, continuously rising temperatures were measured at all stress levels. The values of the equilibrium or the maximum temperature recorded during fatigue tests have been given in Table 1.

It should be noticed that the temperature measured at specimen surfaces for samples tested at 10 Hz sometimes exhibited a lower value than those tested at 5 Hz at the same stress level. This is believed due to the delay in thermal conduction. During fatigue tests at higher load frequencies and higher stress levels, the temperature differences between the center and the surfaces of the specimens are much higher and the specimens may fail before the temperature rises are reflected at their surfaces. Indeed, continuous temperature rises were recorded on specimens tested at 10 Hz even after the fatigue test had been halted upon failure .

Taking this factor into consideration, we may conclude that the decrease in fatigue life of AS4/PEEK $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ laminates with increasing load frequency is directly related to the temperature rise associated with hysteretic heating. This is to say that the effect of load frequency on fatigue life is mainly thermal nature.

Table 1 Results of fatigue tests for $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ APC2/AS-4 samples

Sample#	Frequency (Hz)	Load level % σ_{ult}	Number of cycles	Temperature (°C)
2-B-3	1	60	1,400,000*	34 E
4-B-93	1	60	1,200,000*	32 E
2-C-4	1	65	50700	—
1-A-3	1	70	20650	43 E
1-B-1	1	70	16000	40 E
1-B-8	1	70	21000	45 E
1-B-6	1	70	18800	46 E
3-C-4	1	80	2900	45 E
3-C-22	1	80	3000	45 E
-C-32	1	80	3850	—
1-L-6	1	80	3570	45 E
2-C-2	1	93	1500	—
2-B-2	5	60	100,000	84 F
1-A-4	5	60	186,000	84 F
3-B3	5	70	2200	127 F
3-B-1	5	70	1500	—
1-K-2	5	70	1100	135 F
1-S-5	5	70	2600	152 F
1-A-9	5	70	2620	127 F
1-K-3	5	75	350	100 F
4-B-8	5	80	200	110 F
4-B-7	5	80	220	97 F
1-B-4	5	80	200	108 F
2-D-5	10	60	540	152 F
1-S-1	10	60	575	140 F
1-K-7	10	60	1040	—
1-S-2	10	60	580	—
1-S-8	10	70	450	136 F
1-S-9	10	70	260	95 F
1-K-1	10	70	280	—
1-L-2	10	70	470	119 F
2-D-4	10	75	450	80 F
2-D-2	10	80	200	110 F
2-D-3	10	80	180	102 F
1-S-6	10	80	315	135 F
1-S-7	10	80	120	—
1-A-7	10	80	100	90 F

Sample did not fail after this number of cycles.

E : equilibrium temperature.

F : failure temperature.

A MODEL FOR THERMAL EFFECT ON FATIGUE LIFE

Literature data and our experimental results have shown that thermal degradation associated with hysteretic heating is the dominant frequency effect on fatigue life of thermoplastic composite AS4/PEEK.

For viscoelastic materials, the rate of hysteretic heating is determined by the hysteretic energy dissipated under fatigue loading [9].

$$w = \pi f D''(f, T) \sigma^2 \quad (1)$$

where w = energy dissipated, f = frequency, D'' = the loss compliance, σ = the peak stress.

The hysteretic heating can also be measured directly from the area of hysteretic loop. Hanh and Kim [2] have shown that the hysteretic energy can be approximated by

$$w = C(1-R)^2 \sigma(\sigma - \sigma_t) \quad (2)$$

where C is a parameter related to the mid-width of the hysteretic loop, R is the stress ratio of the fatigue test and σ_t is the threshold stress below which no hysteretic heating is measured. The hysteretic heating rate is given by

$$q = C(1-R)^2 \sigma(\sigma - \sigma_t) f \quad (3)$$

From heat transfer analysis, the equilibrium temperature is found to be proportional to q and hence may be predicted by

$$T = T_0 + \eta' [(1-R)^2 \sigma(\sigma - \sigma_t) f]^\beta \quad (4)$$

where η' and β are parameters, T_0 is the environment temperature.

An observation of S-N curves suggests that these curves may be described by the following function

$$\text{Log}(N)(\sigma - \sigma_0') = C \quad (5)$$

where σ_0' is the fatigue limit, C is a parameter. The strength of viscoelastic materials is sensitive to temperature, so is the fatigue limit. Assuming that the effect of temperature on fatigue limit σ_0' follows an exponential function

$$\sigma_0' = \sigma_0 \exp[-\eta''(T - T_0)] \quad (6)$$

With Eq.4, Eq.6 becomes

$$\sigma_0' = \sigma_0 \exp\{-\eta''[(1-R)^2 \sigma(\sigma - \sigma_t) f]^\beta\} \quad (7)$$

Substitute Eq.7 into Eq.5 and introduce stress parameters $p=\sigma/\sigma_{ult}$, $p_0=\sigma_0/\sigma_{ult}$ and $p_t=\sigma_t/\sigma_{ult}$ we obtain the mathematics model for thermal effect on fatigue life of materials

$$\text{Log}(N)\{p-p_0\exp[-\eta((1-R)^2p(p-p_t)f)^\beta]\}=C \quad (8)$$

Eq.8 is actually a variation of the model presented by Dan-Jumbo et al [5] but, instead of employing the temperature rise data, here the thermal effect is directly related to the stress level and load frequency. In addition, the model in [5] is based on crack growth in viscoelastic media, whereas Eq.8 is based on the assumption of a general strength degradation of the material and hence it is suitable for smooth composite samples.

By curve fitting the data given in Table 1 and with $p_0=0.55$, $p_t=0$ and $R=0.13$, the values of the parameters in Eq.8 were determined as follows: $C=1.7$, $\eta=1$ and $\beta=0.5$. The S-N curves predicted by Eq.8 are presented in Fig.2 by dashed lines to compare with the test data. In general, the model predicted the trend of load frequency effect except for 5 Hz at 60% stress level.

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile fatigue tests of $[45]_{4s}$ AS4/PEEK laminates were carried out at three frequencies: 1 Hz, 5 Hz and 10 Hz. Substantial temperature rises were recorded during fatigue tests, especially at higher frequencies and stress levels. Fatigue life reduced significantly as load frequency increased. The results clearly indicate that the effect of load frequency on fatigue life was dominated by thermal effect. A model correlating thermal effect with load frequency and stress level was proposed. The prediction by the model agreed reasonably well with the test data.

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